

OPTIMIZED SCHEDULING AND BUFFERING OF REPETITIVE CONSTRUCTION PROJECTS UNDER UNCERTAINTY

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ABSTRACT

Construction projects are complex projects that occur in dynamic environments. This fact makes it necessary to take different uncertainties into account during the planning stage. After a thorough review of the literature in Scheduling of Construction Projects, Accounting for Uncertainties Methods, and Buffering, it was found out that there is a lack of tools and programs that take into consideration uncertainties and buffering in repetitive construction projects. Accordingly, this paper presents a framework that is capable of: 1) identifying optimized solution that sets the total cost or duration of the project to the minimum value considering different uncertainties, and 2) providing a tool for building buffers to decrease the possibility of delays in the repetitive construction project. The Research Methodology is composed of two modules; namely: Optimization and Buffering, and was developed into a model which was validated using a case study. Finally, conclusions are drawn and recommendations are identified.

KEYWORDS

Repetitive projects, Uncertainty, Fuzzy Scheduling, Optimization, Genetic Algorithm, Time Buffer, Construction Management

1 INTRODUCTION

Repetitive construction projects are a unique type of construction projects that require construction crews to be timely moved from one unit to its subsequential unit. The repetitive construction projects are classified as typical or non-typical [1]. The typical projects include typical activities having same quantity of work with the same production rates repeated for various units. In general, there exists non-typical projects which include different quantities of work and different production rates for each activity. Accordingly, a repetitive schedule of a project containing different activities consists of activities with different slopes [2] due to different production rates and work quantities as shown in figure 1.

Fig. 1: Typical and Non-Typical Activities

Scheduling of repetitive construction projects is unique because it requires maintaining of work continuity. Therefore, scheduling methods for traditional construction projects such as Critical Path Method (CPM) is considered unsuitable for scheduling these types of projects. This induces the need to develop scheduling methods for repetitive projects since this area of research received less attention compared to other methods developed for scheduling non-repetitive projects. This is also the case of optimized scheduling and for modelling uncertainties in these types of projects.

Accordingly, this paper presents a developed algorithm which accounts for uncertainties pertinent to quantities of work, production rates of crews and costs. In addition, it sizes, aggregates and inserts the required time buffers, which enables users to adjust the size of these buffers to fulfil the desired confidence level in the generated schedule. This algorithm uses genetic algorithm (GA) for optimizing the schedule and fuzzy-set theory to model the uncertainties. Moreover, time buffers are utilized as an approach to protect activities from predicted delays.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

Due to the sheer amount of research addressing this topic, a classification of scheduling techniques has to be performed to permit for better understanding of the available tools and techniques along with their limitations. As shown in figure 2, scheduling of construction projects is classified into two types: scheduling for traditional (non-repetitive) projects, and scheduling for repetitive projects. Each of the two types are further classified into two groups: the first group includes optimization techniques without taking uncertainty into consideration while the other group accounts for stochastic nature of work of repetitive projects through different inputs to these models. In this chapter, each type will be discussed in brief along with a brief account of buffering these types of projects.

Fig. 2: Scheduling of Construction Projects

2.1 Traditional Construction Projects Scheduling

It is known that scheduling construction projects is a challenging process that possesses lots of difficulties and challenges. In fact, there are many techniques utilized for scheduling traditional construction projects such as Critical Path Method (CPM) which does not take uncertainty into account and PERT (Program Evaluation and Review Technique) which accounts for uncertainty.

2.1.1 Deterministic Scheduling of Traditional Construction Projects

The Critical Path method is a well-known algorithm for scheduling traditional construction projects developed in the 1950s. CPM is applied in the construction industry since the 1960s in all sorts of projects[3], [4]. Utilizing software systems such as Primavera and Microsoft Project for scheduling of construction projects has become common across the globe and all these software follow CPM in schedule generation[3]– [5]. However, the CPM technique has reported several drawbacks [8]–[11], which includes the inability to maintain work continuity despite the fact that it is essential to produce a schedule showing uninterrupted resource utilization. Moreover, CPM tend to be too complicated to visualize when it is used to schedule repetitive construction projects, and it is not able to display activities' productivity and location. Furthermore, the number of nodes and the relationships of the complete network will be very large since CPM network shows all the links between similar activities of successive units. In addition, the CPM fails to modify the production rates between similar activities at different units during the well-known time/cost trade-off and hence represent the actual conditions.

2.1.2 Stochastic Scheduling of Traditional Construction Projects

There are some techniques developed to account for the uncertainties associated with non-repetitive construction projects such as the PERT technique which was developed by the US Navy in 1958 as a probabilistic scheduling method used to estimate the probability of project completion. PERT allows users to input three duration estimates (optimistic, most likely and pessimistic) for each activity to account for uncertainty in the activity durations, analyze the probabilistic estimates of activity duration impact on the probability of the overall duration. However, PERT technique has some drawbacks. One of most important drawbacks is that it does not take the impact of subcritical paths on the overall probability of project, thus it may lead to more optimistic results, which leads to unrealistic scheduling of the construction projects[12]. Moreover, it assumes unlimited supply of resources[13].

2.2 Repetitive Construction Projects Scheduling

Despite the vast number of scheduling techniques developed for scheduling traditional projects, none of them were suitable to schedule repetitive construction projects mainly due to the fact that no technique has taken crew work continuity into consideration. Another reason is that it is complicated to visualize the schedule when traditional scheduling methods are used to schedule these types of construction projects. Accordingly, some techniques are developed to schedule only repetitive construction projects.

2.2.1 Deterministic Scheduling of Repetitive Construction Projects

The Line of Balance technique (LOB) is a common scheduling algorithm adapted to schedule repetitive construction projects in which the technique takes into account the work continuity unlike the CPM technique. Furthermore, LOB is found that it requires less time and effort than the CPM technique, provides a better view of the repetitive construction projects, and can produce smoother flow of working crews[14]. However, there are some critics about utilizing LOB technique, which includes the fact that it does not assume that the crews' production rates are varied and non-linear, particularly in repetitive projects with stochastic progress of work. In addition, it cannot identify the critical path efficiently since the production rate is the controlling factor in identifying the criticalness in repetitive projects [15]and it has an assumption that the crews' production rates are constant and linear throughout all units, which may lead to unrealistic scheduling[16].

2.2.2 Stochastic Scheduling of Repetitive Construction Projects

There are some attempts to develop techniques to account for uncertainties in repetitive construction projects and overcome some of the drawbacks associated with the stochastic scheduling of traditional construction projects. A most common technique used was fuzzy-set based scheduling which has been developed to deal with a wide range of real-world problems involving linguistic descriptions [17]. Despite the success that the fuzzy set have shown to account to the uncertain nature of construction projects, it has some limitations including using a specific shape of fuzzy membership to represent the uncertainties and the need of historical data when a hybrid approach is used to integrate Monte Carlo simulation with fuzzy set theory [18].

2.2.3 Buffering of Repetitive Construction Projects Techniques

Building buffers is one of the most important domains in repetitive projects. Buffer is a quintessential element of the repetitive construction projects because main resources are already on-site and what can be stated is that any delay in one activity has more significant cost impact that that in non-repetitive projects. Accordingly, the LOB technique was used to maintain resource continuity and avoid overlapping crew and site congestion during construction phase [19]. Recent attempts showed buffer sizing techniques that can be sorted into two main types. The first class is for building buffers based on historical data in statistical distribution of activities durations. These techniques size buffers based on some factors such as the coefficient of variation, the ratio of standard deviation of an activity's duration to the mean, or the difference between the 90 percent probability of duration completion and the mean duration[20]–[22]. The second class considers buffer sizing techniques given specific factors which increase the delay's impact on the schedule such as the precedence relation of each activity number, or activities' durations. Moreover, this class considers factors presenting uncertainties in economy, law, social and technological environments surrounding the environment[21]– [24].

2.2.4 Optimized Scheduling of Repetitive Construction Projects

This paper focuses on optimization techniques for scheduling of repetitive construction projects which are categorized into two types: deterministic[19], [27], [28] and stochastic[27]– [31]. It is stated from table 1 that the first three references are aimed to address the optimization techniques for scheduling of repetitive construction projects without taking uncertainty into consideration, while the rest of the references addressed the stochastic optimization techniques for scheduling repetitive construction projects.

Table 1: Optimization Methods for Scheduling of Repetitive Construction Projects

Criteria	Reference							
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)
Deterministic	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Stochastic	N	N	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y

Notes: (1) Gracis-Nieves, Ponz-Tienda, Ospina-Alvarado and Bonilla-Palacios (2019); (2) Hunag and Sun (2009); (3) El-Kholy, Sheshtawy, Ragheb and Mohammed (2021); (4) El-Rayes, Zayed and Bakry (2013); (5) Yang and Chang (2005); (6) Hassan, El-Rayes and Attalla (2020); (7) Zhang, Dai, Zou and Qi (2020); and (8) Hassan, El-Rayes and Attalla (2023).

One method developed to optimize the scheduling of repetitive construction projects without taking uncertainty into consideration is linear programming. Although it can produce accurate results, they are not suitable for large-scale projects since they will require enormous computational efforts. For example, the model developed by García-Nieves et al. (2019) suggested to utilize metaheuristic methods to overcome the computational limitations[27]. Metaheuristic methods are utilized to solve large scale problems by performing iterative computation against certain criteria to find near-optimal solutions. They are used inspired from the nature such as Genetic Algorithm (GA). One attempt using the GA made by Hunag and Sun (2009), in which their model utilized the Net Present Value (NPV) to evaluate the different schedule's alternatives' fitness according to a given Minimum Attractive Rate of Return (MARR). However, there is a main limitation that it overlooked the activities' details within each group[28]. Moreover, El-Kholy et al. (2021) a built a model capable for optimizing

schedule for the least total project cost, building buffers to protect the project schedule from expected delays and finding least-cost acceleration plans through accelerating units instead of activities. However, one of its limitations that it is unsuitable for non-linear projects[19].

To account for these uncertainties, some researches are conducted in which the uncertainties are taken into consideration. The second group of researches has an advantage over the first group is that this group includes non-deterministic optimization techniques which managed to take uncertainty into account. One method is the dynamic programming which is a mathematical model which can solve more complex problems and solve linear and non-linear problems. One attempt to utilize this method is made by Bakry et al. (2013), in which their model was capable to account for uncertainties associated with input variables such as quantities, production rates, and costs using the fuzzy set theory and considering the variations in the quantities of work of each activity. However, the model had some limitations including neglecting building buffers to provide protection against delays[33]. One technique used to account for uncertainties in repetitive construction project is the simulation technique which is used to solve more difficult objective function and its goal is to generate random input variables which results in random solution, then each solution is evaluated against the objective function until an optimum solution is found. One attempt using the Simulation technique is made by Yang and Chang (2005) to convert stochastic input into deterministic input using chance-constrained programming (CCP). However, the main disadvantage is that it does not account for delays by inserting buffers[29]. Another attempt is made by Hassan et al. (2020), which accounted for serial and non-serial activities to identify the optimum crew deployment plan that provide the optimum trade-off between expected project duration and expected crew deployment cost. However, this model had some limitations including neglecting the learning curve effect [30]. Another attempt is made by Zhang et al. (2020) by developing a model capable for considered work continuity as a new type of uncertainty factor and investigated how to lessen the negative effects caused by the unexpected interruptions. This model also developed a float-based robustness measurement method. However, the main limitation associated with this model was that it did not take total cost into consideration during the optimization process [31]. One novel multi-objective stochastic scheduling optimization model using the simulation technique was developed by Hassan et al. (2023), which considered all aspects of the total cost including the direct cost, indirect costs, liquidated damaged and incentives. However, there are some limitations associated with this model, including neglecting other types of relationships other than finish-to-start relationship and neglecting multiple crew formation by considering only single crew formation[32]. Table 2 summarizes the main capabilities and limitations associated with different technique of optimization of scheduling of repetitive construction projects.

Table 2: Capabilities and Limitations of Optimization Methods

Criteria	Reference							
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)
Optimization Technique	LP	GA	GA	DP	S	S	S	S
Utilize Buffers	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N
Consider Cost	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	Y
Consider Non-typical activities	N	N	Y	Y	N	Y	N	Y

Notes: LP; linear programming, GA; genetic algorithm, DP; dynamic programming, S; simulation.

3 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

After presenting an extensive literature review about optimization process of scheduling of repetitive construction project under uncertainty, it is clear that the methodology developed in this paper consists of a model which performs schedule optimization, schedule defuzzification, and buffering. The function of this model is identifying the near optimum crew formation that would record the least project duration or the least total cost. Accordingly, a deterministic schedule is generated and time buffers are sized and inserted between activities to provide protection to the protect schedule against predicted delays.

3.1 Optimization Model

This is the first model to be run in the sequences of the proposed methodology. This model’s function is to optimize the schedule of the repetitive construction project under uncertainties effect according to the least total cost possible or least project duration possible to achieve. Moreover, uncertainties must be taken into consideration during this optimization process. Accordingly, features of this model includes maintaining resource work continuity, meeting basic scheduling needs which includes tasks’ duration and calculating project duration and total cost. Figure 3 shows a flowchart summarizing the order which the optimization model will take in this attempt

Fig. 3: Presented Optimization Model Flowchart

3.2 Buffering Model

After optimizing and defuzzifying the repetitive construction project schedule, time buffers are calculated, aggregated and inserted between each pair of consecutive activities in the project. Buffers are determined as isolated activities which have a duration but do not have resources. They are inserted to raise the confidence in meeting the project deadline. In this model, buffers are built taking into account the user’s input of confidence in meeting the planned project duration. This attempt was based on a complete survey, in which it is concluded that it is favourable to account for all possible sources of risk by inserting one buffer rather than building one buffer for each risk source[34]. Figure 4 shows a flowchart summarizing the order which the buffering will take in this attempt.

Fig. 4: Presented Buffering Model Flowchart

4 MODEL DEVELOPMENT

Basic components of the developed method include two models: optimization, defuzzification and buffering model and schedule buffering model. The first model aims to model uncertainty utilizing

fuzzy set theory and transforming fuzzy input variables into deterministic values. Moreover, its function is to identify the optimum crew formation that satisfies a single objective function whether the objective is based on the total cost of the project or the total duration of the project. The Genetic Algorithm (GA) is particularly suited for this problem because it operates in a set of solutions rather than one single solution and this makes the GA the most suitable search engine for complicated problems which include uncertainties.

4.1 Optimization Model Development

The developed optimization model firstly calculates the fuzzy activity durations based on user's input shown in figure 5 such as the most probable production rates for each activity, the optimistic and pessimistic production rate factor, the most probable quantities for each activity and the optimistic and pessimistic quantity factor. Fuzzy activity durations which depend on fuzzy quantities and productivity rates are calculated utilizing equation (1) for all processes. The fuzzy schedule is sequenced using equations (2) and (3) and the duration of the project is calculated utilizing equation (4).

$$d_{[a,b,c]}^{i,j} = [(Q_{[a]}^{i,j}/P_{[c]}), (Q_{[b]}^{i,j}/P_{[b]}), (Q_{[c]}^{i,j}/P_{[a]})] \quad (1)$$

$$IS_{[a,b,c]}^{i,j} = \text{Max} (IF_{[a,b,c]}^{i-1,j}, IF_{[a,b,c]}^{i,j-1}) \quad (2)$$

$$IF_{[a,b,c]}^{i,j} = [(IS_{[a]}^{i,j} + d_{[a]}^{i,j}), (IS_{[b]}^{i,j} + d_{[b]}^{i,j}), (IS_{[c]}^{i,j} + d_{[c]}^{i,j})] \quad (3)$$

$$PD_{[a,b,c]} = IF_{[a,b,c]}^{m,n} \quad (4)$$

Where; $d_{[a,b,c]}^{i,j}$ Fuzzy duration of unit i in activity j
 $Q_{[a,b,c]}^{i,j}$ Fuzzy quantity of unit i in activity j
 $P_{[a,b,c]}$ Fuzzy production rate of crews
 $IS_{[a,b,c]}^{i,j}$ Fuzzy initial start date of unit i in activity j
 $IF_{[a,b,c]}^{i,j}$ Fuzzy initial finish date of unit i in activity j
 $PD_{[a,b,c]}$ Fuzzy total project duration
 $IF_{[a,b,c]}^{m,n}$ Fuzzy initial finish date of last unit m in last activity n

Factors Production Rate			Factors Quantity			Production Rate			Quantity			Duration			Labour Cost / Day	Equipment Cost/Day	Material Cost / Quantity
c	b	a	c	b	a	c	b	a	c	b	a	a	b	c			
1.15	1	0.9	1	1	1	105.5	91.75	82.58	1529	1529	1529	14.5	16.7	18.5	566	340	0
1.25	1	0.8	1	1	1	67.33	53.86	43.09	896	896	896	13.3	16.6	20.8	1902	436	92
1	1	1	1.25	1	0.95	5.73	5.73	5.73	125	100	95	16.6	17.5	21.8	1875	285	479
1	1	1	1	1	1	5.66	5.66	5.66	80	80	80	14.1	14.1	14.1	1850	148	195
1.25	1	0.9	1	1	1	9.7	7.76	6.984	145	145	145	14.9	18.7	20.8	1878	149	186

Figure 4: Basic Schedule Data in Excel Model

For this model, total cost (TC) is calculated utilizing equation (5) and it considers total direct cost (TDC) and total indirect cost (TIDC). Direct cost is calculated using equation (6) that includes labour costs, equipment costs and material costs. Labour and equipment costs are functions of activities duration, whereas material costs are function of material quantities. Total indirect costs are calculated using equation (7).

$$TC_{[a,b,c]} = TDC_{[a,b,c]} + TIDC_{[a,b,c]} \quad (5)$$

$$TDC_{[a,b,c]} = \sum_{i=0}^m \sum_{j=0}^n \left[\left((L_{[a,b,c]}^{i,j} + E_{[a,b,c]}^{i,j}) \times d_{[a,b,c]}^{i,j} \right) + M_{[a,b,c]}^{i,j} \times Q_{[a,b,c]}^{i,j} \right] \quad (6)$$

$$TIDC_{[a,b,c]} = IC_{[a,b,c]} \times PD_{[a,b,c]} \quad (7)$$

Where; $TC_{[a,b,c]}$ Fuzzy total cost of the project
 $TDC_{[a,b,c]}$ Fuzzy total direct cost of the project
 $TIDC_{[a,b,c]}$ Fuzzy total indirect cost of the project

- $L_{[a,b,c]}^{i,j}$ Fuzzy labour cost per unit time of unit i in activity j
- $E_{[a,b,c]}^{i,j}$ Fuzzy equipment cost per unit time of unit i in activity j
- $M_{[a,b,c]}^{i,j}$ Fuzzy material cost per unit quantity of activity j in unit i
- $d_{[a,b,c]}^{i,j}$ Fuzzy duration of one activity of activity j in unit i
- $IC_{[a,b,c]}$ Fuzzy indirect cost per unit time

The model uses the fuzzy set theory to present the uncertainties for various fuzzy inputs which are bases on the user’s experience to model inputs utilizing triangular fuzzy numbers if users have no ability to provide crisp inputs. A triangular fuzzy number is presented by three numbers a, b, c. Each of the numbers is associated with membership values of 0, 1 and 0 respectively. Uncertainties are modeled in production rates of crew, quantities of each activity, direct costs and indirect costs. After all fuzzy inputs are determined by the user and the fuzzy outputs are calculated, they are defuzzied using the center of area (COA) method [18] for all fuzzy outputs. The expected value of a triangular fuzzy number is calculated utilizing equation (8).

$$EV = \frac{a+b+c}{3} \tag{8}$$

- Where; EV Expected value of a triangular fuzzy number
- a The least possible value of a set of fuzzy number
- b The most likely value of a set of fuzzy number
- c The largest possible value of a set of fuzzy number

Selected Main Crew Formation	No of Main Crew	Selected Secondary Crew 01 Formation	No of Secondary Crew 01
1	1	1	0
3	1	2	0
1	1	3	0
4	1	3	0
2	1	1	0
0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0

Figure 5: Variables Cells in The Model (Crew Formations and Their Numbers)

Costs (Fuzzy)									Duration (Fuzzy)		
TDC (Fuzzy)			TIDC (Fuzzy)			Total Cost (Fuzzy)			a	b	c
a	b	c	a	b	c	a	b	c	a	b	c
1,216,835.09	1,317,371.16	1,457,798.59	121,730.47	142,900.69	168,448.92	1,338,565.56	1,460,271.86	1,626,247.51	121.7	142.9	168.4

Cost				Duration
TDC	TIDC	TC		
1,330,688.28	144,360.03	1,475,028.31	144.4	

Figure 6: Objective Cell (Total Cost and Project Duration) in The Model

The model is then formulated into an excel spreadsheet tool to minimize total cost equation (5) or total project duration equation (04) for repetitive scheduling as shown in figure 5 by changing the variable value of selected main crew formation and secondary crew formation shown in figure 6, given constraints addressing activities logical relationships and crew formations.

The problem is solved by evolutionary solving method which resembles a genetic algorithm (GA) optimization software. Genetic Algorithm is a method that merge natural genetic operators with an artificial strategy of the fittest strategy to form a technique which is suitable to solve complex optimization problems[35]. The procedure begins by generating an initial set of solutions encoded in form of strings called chromosomes which represents a better or worse solution than other solutions in the problem. After that, each chromosome’s fitness is evaluated based on how much its performance satisfies a certain objective function. When a new offspring gene is created, two chromosomes are chosen from the populations, which depends mainly on a rank-based mechanism. This mechanism offers a smoother probability curve for selection. Best chromosomes (solutions) exchange information to create offspring genes which replace less fit members in the population by simulating natural survival of the fittest process. The process is done several times, while the best set of solutions replace less fit solutions until a closing criterion is reached which means that one answer becomes satisfactory. Finally, the set of solutions which showed the best performance is selected as near optimum solutions.

4.2 Buffering Model Development

After defuzzifying and optimizing the schedule of the project, time buffers are built and inserted to provide protection for the repetitive project against delays and to increase confidence in meeting the project deadline. The buffer building calculations uses the crisp values to evaluate the number of uncertainties associated with each activity. The buffer building algorithm builds one single buffer for each activity to account for all uncertainties which affect each activity. In fact, it is essential to input the user's desired confidence in the generated schedule's duration because repetitive projects take place in different circumstances and under various conditions and each project manager is willing to accept a certain amount of risks. In this model, agreement index (AI) is utilized to present the users' desired confidence in the project's final duration. AI is an index and its value ranges between 0 and 1 showing the conformity of two fuzzy events. It is calculated as the ratio between the intersection area of the two area and the first event's area. Accordingly, after calculating the shift required to ensure work continuity using equation (9) as shown in figure 7, the user choose the suitable AI value and the algorithm calculates the corresponding crisp duration that satisfies the given AI using equation (10). Buffers are defined as the difference between the deterministic duration between the specified AI and the expected value EV of the fuzzy durations. Buffers are calculated for each unit separately, aggregated into one single buffer and then is inserted for each activity at the least duration between two consecutive activities. Such shift is calculated by equation (11). The least duration between two activities is at the unit at which the maximum first shift was calculated using equation (9). The final start and finish dates for each activity are calculated using equations (12) and (13), while the total project duration and the total project cost are calculated using equations (14) and (15) respectively.

$$Shift_{I^j} = Max_{i=0}^{i=m} (IS^{i,j} - IF^{i,j-1}) \quad (9)$$

$$Dur_{AI} = c - \sqrt{(1 - AI)(c - b)(c - a)} \quad (10)$$

$$Shift_{II^j} = \sum_{i=0}^{i=U} \left[(c - \sqrt{(1 - AI)(c - b)(c - a)}) - \frac{a+b+c}{3} \right] \quad (11)$$

$$S^{i,j} = IS^{i,j} + Shift_{I^j} + Shift_{II^j} \quad (12)$$

$$F^{i,j} = IF^{i,j} + Shift_{I^j} + Shift_{II^j} \quad (13)$$

$$PD = F^{m,n} \quad (14)$$

$$TC = \sum_{i=0}^m \sum_{j=0}^n \left[((L^{i,j} + E^{i,j}) \times d^{i,j}) + M^{i,j} \times Q^{i,j} \right] + (IC \times PD) \quad (15)$$

Where; $Shift_{I^j}$	The needed shift to ensure work continuity
$Shift_{II^j}$	The needed shift to accommodate inserted buffers
$IS^{i,j}$	Initial start date of unit i in activity j
$IF^{i,j}$	Initial finish date of unit i in activity j
a, b and c	Three values forming the fuzzy duration (See equation (8))
AI	The desired agreement index
U	The unit at which maximum shift I is located
$S^{i,j}$	Start date of unit i in activity j after taking buffers into consideration
$F^{i,j}$	Finish date of unit i in activity j after taking buffers into consideration
PD	Total project duration
m	The total number of units in project
n	The total number of activities in project
$L^{i,j}$	Labour cost per unit time of unit i in activity j
$E^{i,j}$	Equipment cost per unit time of unit i in activity j
$M^{i,j}$	Material cost per unit quantity of unit i in activity j
$d^{i,j}$	Duration of activity j in unit i
IC	Indirect cost per unit time

ID	Activity	Duration			Dur (EV)	Dur (AI)	Buffer	ES (EV)	EF (EV)	Shift_I	Shift_II	Start	Finish
		a	b	c									
1	A	14.5	16.7	18.5	16.6	17.7	1.1	38.7	55.3	0.0	3.7	38.7	55.3
2	B	13.3	16.6	20.8	16.9	19.0	2.1	70.0	86.9	0.0	9.3	70.0	86.9
3	C	16.6	17.5	21.8	18.6	20.3	1.7	92.7	111.4	0.0	7.3	100.5	119.1
4	D	14.1	14.1	14.1	14.1	14.1	0.0	111.9	126.0	1.3	0.0	120.0	134.2
5	E	14.9	18.7	20.8	18.1	19.7	1.5	126.2	144.4	1.4	4.2	146.3	164.5
6	F	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
7	G	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
8	H	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
9	I	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
10	J	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
11	K	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
12	L	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
13	M	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
14	N	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
15	O	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
16	End	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	144.4	144.4	0.0	0.0	164.5	164.5

Figure 7: Excel Spreadsheet Showing the Calculations of Buffers

5 CASE STUDY

A case study of concrete bridge was taken from literature. Some analysis was performed on this case study by several researchers[26], [36]–[39]. The concrete bridge project consists of four major units, and each unit contain five concurrent activities: excavation, foundations, columns, beams and slabs as shown in figure 8. These activities are considered on-typical activities because work quantities and production rates differ from one unit to another. Each activity is carried out by a set of crews and each crew has its own production rate and cost. Table 3 shows the costs of each crew formation and materials in each activity. To account for uncertainties associated with the input related to crews and activities, the same fuzzy numbers used by Bakry et al. (2016) were utilized to enable a comparison, as shown in table 4. These fuzzy numbers shown in table 6 present the uncertainties associated with the production rates of crews of excavation, foundations, beams and slabs activities and the quantities of materials of columns activity. Indirect cost of this project was assumed to be \$1,000 per day as shown in the literature which analyzed the case study[26], [36]–[39].

Fig. 8: Three-Span Reinforced Concrete Bridge Case Study

Table 3: Direct Costs of Each Type of Resource for Each Activity

Activity	Crew	Labour Cost (\$/day)	Equipment Cost (\$/day)	Material Cost (\$/day)
Excavation (A)	1	566	340	0
	1	3,804	874	92
Foundation (B)	2	2,853	655	92
	3	1,902	436	92
Columns (C)	1	1,875	285	479
	2	2,438	371	479
	3	3,000	456	479
Beams (D)	1	3,931	315	195
	2	3,238	259	195
	3	2,544	204	195
	4	1,850	148	195
Slabs (E)	1	2,230	177	186

Table 4: Input of Fuzzy Quantities and Production Rates for Activities

Activity	Crew	Fuzzy Quantities (m ³)												Fuzzy Crew Output (m ³ /day)		
		Section 1			Section 2			Section 3			Section 4			a	b	c
Excavation (A)	1	1147			1434			994			1529			82.6	91.8	105.5
	$\frac{1}{2}$	1032			1077			943			890			85.3	89.8	103.2
Foundation (B)	$\frac{2}{3}$	1032			1077			943			890			61.0	71.8	82.6
	$\frac{3}{3}$	1032			1077			943			890			43.1	53.9	61.9
Columns (C)	$\frac{1}{2}$	94	104	130	88	92	110	103	129	155	95	100	125	5.7	5.7	5.7
	$\frac{2}{3}$													6.9	6.9	6.9
Beams (D)	$\frac{3}{4}$	85			92			101			80			8.0	8.0	8.0
	$\frac{4}{4}$	85			92			101			80			9.9	9.9	9.9
Slabs (E)	$\frac{1}{2}$	0			138			114			145			8.5	8.5	8.5
	$\frac{2}{2}$	0			138			114			145			7.1	7.1	7.1
		0			138			114			145			5.7	5.7	5.7
		0			138			114			145			7.9	8.7	10.5
		0			138			114			145			7.0	7.8	9.8

The aim of the first run in this case study was to check that the developed algorithm can verify the results of the analysis of the original case generated by the developed model for the deterministic optimization of scheduling of the repetitive projects by El-Rayes (1997) for the optimum group of crews that would yield the least project total cost. For this run, the deterministic input employed by El-Rayes (1997) are presented as triangular fuzzy numbers. In other words, a crew output of 8.7 m³/day is determined as 8.7, 8.7 and 8.7 m³/day respectively. This run testifies the ability of the algorithm to validly complete the optimization process utilizing fuzzy numbers. The run starts as shown in figure 3 by generating the initial crew formation and calculating the total cost and duration from equations (01) to (07). The fitness of this crew formation is identified by evaluating this performance against the objective function which is the least total cost in this run. Best genes (solutions) exchange data to produce offspring (other better or worse pairs of solutions) that are assessed and can be retained only if they are better and fitter than others in the population. This process is continued for many offspring generations until a near optimum gene is found.

The second run's purpose is to generate a near optimized schedule that yield the total cost of the project with taking uncertainties into account and then adding buffer between each two consecutive activities in the project. The second run has three aims: 1) to verify the results of the analysis of the case study provided by the developed for the stochastic optimization of repetitive projects by Bakry et al. (2016) for the optimum crews group that yield the total least cost, 2) to compare the results with that of the first run and 3) to investigate the effect of adding the buffers on the optimized schedule which yield the least total cost of the project. Any user can use his experience and judgement to present uncertainty by inputting three values for production rates and quantities. These three values are identified as the smallest, most likely and the greatest value the input can have. The fuzzified values are illustrated in table 4. The run's procedures are similar to the first run, except that it performs defuzzification as stated in equation (7) and then generates a near optimized schedule then it regenerates the schedule after buffering it. A user input agreement index (AI) of 0.9 is used to size and insert the required buffers. Buffers are sized according to the difference between the expected value (EV) of duration and the duration having an AI of 0.9. Both shifts are calculated for both ensuring work continuity and accommodate the inserted buffers using equations (9) and (10). Figures 11 and 12 shows the optimized schedule with no buffering and the optimized schedule with buffering, respectively. Both schedules in figures 11 and 12 yield the least total cost of the project

The objective of the third run is to determine the near optimum crew formation that would yield the least duration schedule. This run will enable comparing its results with the schedules generated in the second run. This run utilizes the same fuzzy input in table 4 and the same agreement index (AI) of 0.9 for buffering to enable accurate comparison. Figures 13 and 14 shows the optimized schedule

with no buffering and the optimized schedule with buffering, respectively. Both schedules in figures 11 and 12 yield the least duration of the project

5.1 Analysis of Results

Testing of the developed algorithm through the three described runs let to several observations. The first run determines the optimum crew formation that yield the least total cost as $A_1B_3C_1D_4E_2$, which is the same crew formation identified by the deterministic model developed by El-Rayes (1997). The project total cost has an EV equal to \$1,460,273 in comparison to \$1,458,799 by El-Rayes (1997). There is a difference of about 1% and is attributed to the activity durations' approximations in the original case. Moreover, the first run produced a schedule with duration of 143 days, which is the same exact duration the algorithm of El-Rayes (1997) has identified. Figures 9 and 10 show the original schedule and the deterministic optimized schedule that yield the total project cost.

Fig. 9: Original Schedule

Fig. 10: Deterministic Optimized Schedule (Least Total Cost)

The second run aims at finding the least cost producing one optimized schedule without buffering and another schedule after buffering the schedule. Both schedules consider using fuzzy inputs. Both schedules identifies the optimum crew formation of $A_1B_3C_1D_4E_2$, which is the same as the first run. The resulting EVs of the total cost and duration are \$1,475,028 and 145 days respectively, which is nearly the same values as produced by the algorithm developed by Bakry et al. (2016). These results shows the impact of taking uncertainties into account; despite the fact that this change in input to account for uncertainty leads to production of the same optimum crew formation, it determined an increase in the total cost and the duration as shown in figures 10 and 11. This happened because the fuzzified input parameters lrd to a slighter higher EV than the determistic optimized schedule. Furthermore, it is obseved, as shown in figure 12, that the optimized schedule that yield the least total cost has recorded \$1,495,119 and 165 days as total project cost and duration of the project respectively after buffering the project. Figures 11 and 12 shows that the defuzzified and the buffered schedule has a longer duration and higher total cost than the defuzzified schedule. This longer duration happens due to the inserted buffers, while the higher total cost happens due to the increase in the indirect cost due to the inserted buffers.

Fig. 11: Stochastic Optimized Schedule (Least Total Cost) (Without Buffers)

Fig. 12: Stochastic Optimized Schedule (Least Total Cost) (With Buffers)

The objective of the third run is to test the algorithm ability to find the near optimum spkution that would yield the least duration, utilizing the same input as the second run. The third tun identified $A_1B_1C_3D_1E_1$ as the optimum crew formation. This crew formation yielded \$1,520,317 and 106 days as the total project cost and project duration before buffering, while the crew formation recorded \$ 1,535,858 and 122 days as total project cost and duration respectively after bulding and inserting buffers. The results of this run confirm the effect of buffering stated previously in the second run. Moreover, the generated schedules shown in figures 13 and 14 have a shorter duration and higher costs than those generated in the second run and this is rationally expected because the algorithm chooses crews having higher producivity and thus more costly in the least duration optimization. Figures 15 and 16 shows the summaries of the results of deterministic scheduling and stochastic scheduling respectively.

Fig. 13: Stochastic Optimized Schedule (Least Duration) (Without Buffers)

Fig. 14: Stochastic Optimized Schedule (Least Duration) (With Buffers)

Fig. 15: Comparison Between Original Schedule and Deterministic Optimization Approach

Fig. 16: Comparison Between Original Schedule and Different Stochastic Cases

6 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This paper represented an algorithm for optimized scheduling and buffering of repetitive construction projects taking projects' uncertainties into consideration. The developed algorithm address two issues presented in the literature review section, which are 1) the lack of stochastic scheduling optimization techniques, and 2) lack of building buffering models. The algorithm accounts for uncertainties associated with repetitive projects by utilizing fuzzy numbers to allow the user to account for uncertainties with work quantities and crew production rates. The buffering process uses these fuzzy inputs to evaluate uncertainties associated with each individual activity, and agreement index (AI) to identify the desired users' confidence level in the produced schedule, hence, producing a comprehensive algorithm addressing the previous techniques' limitations. This algorithm provides planners with a tool to produce project plans that present projects' environments more accurately. Furthermore, it stimulates them to depart from the luxury and ease of neglecting projects' uncertainties and employ their experience towards generating more accurate project schedules. Several conclusions were drawn from the through evaluation of three different scenarios of the case

study. The genetic algorithm technique utilized can successfully of locating the least total cost or least duration under projects' uncertainties while maintaining work continuity. Moreover, the model can successfully replicate the deterministic results provided by the previous models. The optimization model showed the ease of using the expected values (EVs) of the optimized fuzzy schedules to evaluated the uncertainty amount impacting individual activities. In addition, the buffering model is capable of capturing the user's needed confidence level in the schedule by using the agreement index; hence, it can insert time buffers. When combining the two models together, the optimization model along with the buffering model provide construction planners with a tool for producing a near optimized schedule for repetitive construction projects, which it addresses uncertainties and is protected with time buffers.

Future work is encouraged to expand the presented algorithm boundaries, particularly in the fields of accounting for learning curve effect, experimenting with other fuzzy distribution rather than the triangular fuzzy distribution, allowing for multi-objective optimization, and presenting methods for monitoring and controlling the repetitive construction projects such as buffer consumption of individual activities and the repetitive project.

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